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Mardanova Guljahon Furqatkizi

Scientific researcher of
Samarkand state institute of foreign languages

EXPRESSION OF THE CONCEPT OF "WEALTH" IN PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS OF UZBEK LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, one of the urgent issues of modern linguistics is the study of certain concepts. Folk culture, in turn, has a linguistic expression. The interest in studying this issue is related to the fact that modern scientists have repeatedly turned to the issue of the connection between language, thinking and spiritual culture of a person in recent times. The concept of "wealth" is one of the main concepts for understanding the peoples of the world. Because in our time it is a certain measure of happiness. In this regard, this article analyzes the concept of "wealth" in Uzbek folk proverbs. Because with the help of proverbs, it is possible to determine the common and different features of the perception of the world by different peoples, to show the image of the world and its concepts in proverbs, and also to compare the mentality of the people with the mentality of other nations.

Keywords: Concept, proverb, paremiology, proverb, folklore, linguocultural meaning.

Марданова Гулжахон Фуркат кизи

Научный соискатель Самаркандского государственного
института иностранных языков

ВЫРАЖЕНИЕ КОНЦЕПТА «БОГАТСТВО» В ПАРЕМИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЕДИНИЦАХ УЗБЕКСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В настоящее время одним из актуальных вопросов современного языкознания является исследование некоторых понятий. Народная культура, в свою очередь, имеет языковое выражение. Интерес к изучению этого вопроса связан с тем, что современные ученые в последнее время неоднократно обращались к вопросу о связи языка, мышления и духовной культуры человека. Понятие «богатство» является одним из основных понятий для понимания народов мира. Потому что в наше время это определенная мера счастья. В связи с этим в данной статье анализируется понятие «богатство» в узбекских народных пословицах. Потому что с помощью пословиц можно определить общие и различные черты восприятия мира разными народами, показать в пословицах образ мира и его понятия, а также сравнить менталитет народа с менталитет других народов.

Ключевые слова: Концепт, паремия, паремиология, пословица, фольклор, лингвокультурное значение.

Mardanova Guljahon Furqatqizi
Samarqand davlat chet tillat instituti
mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

O'ZBEK TILINING PAREMIOLOGIK BIRLIKLARIDA "BOYLIK" KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI

ANNOTATSIYA

Hozirgi kunda zamonaviy tilshunoslikning dolzarb masalalaridan biri muayyan tushunchalarni o'rganishdir. Xalq madaniyati, o'z navbatida, lisoniy ifodaga ega. Bu masalani o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqish zamonaviy olimlarning so'nggi paytlarda insonning tili, tafakkuri va ma'naviy madaniyati o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik masalasiga qayta-qayta murojaat qilishlari bilan bog'liq. "Boylik" konsepti dunyo xalqlarini tushunish uchun asosiy tushunchalardan biridir. Chunki bizning davrimizda bu baxtning ma'lum bir o'lchovidir. Shu munosabat bilan, ushbu maqolada o'zbek xalq maqollaridagi "boylik" tushunchasi tahlil qilinadi. Chunki maqollar yordamida turli xalqlarning dunyoni idrok etishidagi umumiy va farqli xususiyatlarni aniqlash, maqollarda olam va undagi tushunchalarning tasvirini ko'rsatish, shuningdek, xalqning namoyon bo'lgan mentalitetini boshqa millat mentalitetiga solishtirish mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Konsept, paremiya, paremiologiya, maqol, xalq og'zaki ijodi, lingvomadaniy qiymat.

Introduction. In the field of world linguistics, the system of wise expressions-including proverbs, sayings, and aphorisms-are categorized as paremiological units, regarded as exemplary masterpieces of human thought. "These units within the paremiological system encapsulate conclusions derived from "observations of universal laws, grounded in life experiences. They embody societal attitudes, mental states, ethical and aesthetic sensibilities, and positive attributes. Transmitted orally across generations, they are succinct, concise, and convey profound logical summaries..".

A proverb is a short fable. This is a judgment, a doctrine expressed in an oblique form and put into circulation [3, p 385]. Proverb is an extremely compact and at the same time surprisingly capacious and deeply meaningful genre of oral creativity that has developed over many centuries on the basis of the socio-economic, political and cultural experience of the people [11, p 112].

According to the linguistic encyclopedic dictionary, a proverb is defined as a brief, stable expression, often characterized by a rhythmic structure, which encapsulates the collective experience of a people accumulated over centuries [7, p 389].

V.P. According to Zhukov, a proverb is not a simple saying that expresses the opinion of the people. Since every proverb has not become a proverb, but only a proverb that fits the lifestyle and opinions of many people, such a proverb can be passed from century to century and exist for thousands of years. Behind every proverb is the reputation of the generation that created them. Therefore, proverbs do not argue, do not prove - they confirm or deny something with the confidence that everything they say is strictly true [6, p 122]. The source of proverbs is proverbs, sayings, aphorisms, which are included in the section of philology called paremiology. Proverbs as an object of scientific research can be studied from a scientific point of view both in speech and in language at the same time, that is, in the text and in the system. Proverbs are considered a completely independent text, and the message in any communication has a cognitive, pragmatic meaning [5, p 206]. To determine the message, it is necessary to have a general fund of knowledge, but, in our opinion, this feature is not only characteristic of any text, message, but also applies to proverbs as a completely independent text. Most importantly, such a set of common knowledge unites representatives of the same ethnic, social and cultural community. This makes it possible to consider proverbs and sayings from a linguistic and cultural point of view.

S.I. Ojegov defines a proverb as "a short folk proverb with an instructive content, a folk aphorism" [4, p 112], that is, proverbs appear among the people in folk oral creativity, they are based on the people's many years of life experience, represents its history, lifestyle, culture, and development.

On the one hand, proverbs are "philosophical sayings", "educations", "aphorisms" about various aspects of life [3, p 14], on the other hand, they are units with a high psychological and educational level. These are "the code of ethics", "the assessment of existence" [6, p 74], as well as the cultural wealth of the people and a rhetorical tool used strategically.

The semantic nature of the proverb, A.I. As Molotkov noted, it is based on judgment [8, p 16]. The duality of the proverbial expression consists of a direct and allegorical plan of the content of the sentence, and is connected with the condition of the genre - their proverbial nature, because they are a product of folk art.

A.N. Baranov and D.O. Dobrovolsky defines proverbs as phraseological units with a sentence structure, in fact, the idea of commonality in them indicates the semantics and discursive independence of the doctrine of recommendation or advice (moral education)" [9, p 69].

A.V. Kunin calls proverbs communicative phraseological units, distinguishes psychological and didactic meaning, rhythmically organized paremiological unit from the important features of proverbs [3, p 45].

When we usually encounter a proverb in a text, "regardless of the form of speech, spoken, written, in context or out of context" [10, p15], we almost always understand it to be a proverb, a proverb and the words in it. We understand what it means, what it is about, even if it is not in the existing meanings of ordinary language.

The purpose of this study is to determine the expression of the concept of "Wealth" in proverbs or in other words "paremiological units". The concept of "wealth" is one of the main concepts for understanding the peoples of the world. Because in our time it is a certain measure of happiness. Because with the help of proverbs, it is possible to identify the common and different features of the perception of the world by different nations, to show the image of the world and its concepts in proverbs, as well as to compare the mentality of a nation with the mentality of another nation.

The concept is a universal phenomenon, so its application helps to create a universal image of the world. A set of concepts specific to a particular nation constitutes a field of national concepts that differ from existing concepts in other nations. Despite the existence of concepts accepted as universal, their content may differ to a certain extent for each nation.

The main goal of this article is to study the concept of "wealth" in the Uzbek language. This concept refers to linguistic and cultural concepts. Lingvokulturology is a complex of scientific knowledge resulting from the interaction and influence of language and culture. In the 90s of the 20th century, a new branch of science, linguoculturology (linguistics) appeared between linguistics and cultural studies. It would not be wrong to say that this field was one of the biggest achievements in linguistics. Because behind this line of linguistics great achievements, innovations and changes came to science. It was recognized as an independent direction in linguistics. Almost all researchers about the formation of linguoculturalology claim that the roots of this theory of linguistics go back to V. von Humboldt. By the beginning of the 21st century, linguistic and cultural studies have become one of the leading directions in world linguistics. Lingvokulturology is a science that studies language as a cultural phenomenon, and its subject is language and culture in mutual relationship. The views on the "rich and poor" of the countries, which are the subject of our article, are also studied in this way in linguistic and cultural studies. These things are the main learning tool of linguistic and cultural studies. V. N. Teliya writes about this: "Linguocultural science is a science that deals with the human factor, more precisely, the cultural factor in a person. This means that the center of linguistic and cultural studies is a complex of achievements typical of the anthropological paradigm of the human being as a cultural phenomenon. Whether certain times are "rich or poor" depends on the human factor. V. N. Teliya's opinion is justified when viewed in this way. The main task of every state and country is to save its citizens and society from poverty, both materially and spiritually, and make them rich. These aspects are definitely rooted in culture. Lingvokulturology studies the connection between man and culture. Nobody wants to be poor. Wealth brings great benefits to humanity itself, to society, and to the country. Every country wants to lead society towards wealth. That is why views of wealth and poverty are the same in almost all countries. It is not correct to think of wealth only in terms of material wealth. A person should strive to be spiritually rich, mature, and mature. No one

can defeat a nation rich in spirituality. A person who does not have a lot of money, a contented person is rich, not a person who has everything, but a person who has something that cannot be bought is rich. If one is materially mature, but spiritually poor, this is considered the greatest weakness. Sages also said - "Strive for knowledge." If you don't have money, you won't face poverty with your knowledge, if you are rich, your knowledge will make you beautiful." This is not said for nothing. No one can beat a knowledgeable, spiritually rich person. Material wealth can sometimes go out of a person's hands, or even be lost at some point. And no one can ever take away a thoroughly acquired knowledge. Some people think that silver and gold are blessings, but in fact, wealth is only one of the means of obtaining blessings. Almost all people are like this: they grieve when they lose their wealth, but they never regret the wasted days of their life, the time that flows like a flowing river. After all, the life given to us is the most valuable wealth. These things also show how much humanity is attached to wealth. Wealth is compared to the salt water of the sea. The more you drink, the thirstier you will be. A person is never satisfied with wealth. He does not even realize that his life is coming to an end chasing wealth. True, poverty is not something to be envied, no one wants it. But a person who knows how to live even in poverty is considered the owner of a truly noble virtue. Above all, poverty teaches a person contentment and patience. A spiritually rich person understands this and looks for wisdom from poverty and ways to get out of it. A spiritually poor person only complains about his poverty all his life and never tries to get rid of it. For this reason, a spiritually poor person is equal to everything. A spiritually mature person will certainly find his place. A person is not only materially poor, the increase of greed is also poverty. A person should be eager for something, not only at the level of greed. But Democritus says the following thoughts: "A rich person who needs something is not rich, a poor person who does not need anything is not poor. People are not corrupted by wealth or poverty, they are led astray by greed and avarice. Poverty can be a problem, but it shows what a person is capable of. The biggest secret of rich people is that they know what wealth is measured by. Wealth is not actually measured with money; wealth is measured in time. A person who wastes his time can neither gain wealth nor knowledge.

The concept of "wealth" is a prominent topic in contemporary discourse. This prominence stems from the increasing perception of tangible assets as highly valuable among many individuals. Proverbs play a crucial role in characterizing a culture, often regarded as a "treasure of folk wisdom." They offer insights into the character and mentality of a specific people, making them particularly valuable to researchers.

Therefore, different schools and approaches are emerging in the coverage of these issues. The most popular types of research are linguocognitive and linguo-cultural. From the point of view of linguistic culture, the concept is like a piece of culture in the human mind, in the form of which culture enters the spiritual world of a person. Concept, on the other hand, is seen as a means by which a person himself enters into, and in some cases influences, culture.

Linguistic-cognitive studies have a typological orientation and are aimed at determining the general laws of forming mental images. They focus on the semasiological direction: from meaning (concept) to language (the means of verbalizing it).

Linguistic culture studies the relationship between language and culture, which is manifested in the ways of linguistic expression of ethnic mentality. Thus, the interest of linguoculturalists is focused on the study of what is unique in the structure of mental units and on the systematic description of the specific semantic features of specific cultural concepts. Nevertheless, the tendency is that linguistic and cultural studies, on the contrary, are onomasiologically oriented, going from the name of a concept to the set of meanings it indicates.

The concept of wealth in the Uzbek language has a clear national character. In linguistics, wealth in the meaning of the word gives a feeling of peace and satisfaction with life, implies the existence of not only a large amount of material goods, but also a sufficient amount for the owner and gradually accumulates.

S.G. According to Vorkachev, there is a "cognitive memory of the word", which is related to the semantic features of the linguistic sign, its original purpose, the national mentality and the system of spiritual values of native speakers.

The identified primary conceptual features of the lexeme "wealth" confirm the special role of the described concept in human well-being:

1. Initially, wealth was associated with the concepts of "property, status, share, giver".
2. Wealth structurally corresponds to the Latin word "fortunatus" and has definitions such as "happiness, fate".
3. Wealth is the opposite of poverty.

V.I. In Dahl's explanatory dictionary, the lexeme "wealth" is understood as follows:

1. A large amount of money, any property, etc.;
2. Abundant life, great quantity or price of something.'

The dictionary of synonyms in the Uzbek language gives the following definitions for the lexical unit "wealth":

- 1). goodness, prosperity, happiness;
- 2). to own a lot of something: a lot of things that are the object of human desires, a lot of earthly possessions, prosperity, wealth;
- 3). rich reserves: large savings, wealth;
- 4). all property having monetary value or valuable in any exchange;
- 5). all material objects of economic importance; especially stocks of useful goods that always have economic value.

Analysis of these dictionary entries allows us to conclude that wealth for the people is primarily related to material values that ensure comfortable living. In addition, synonyms of this representative lexeme have been identified, which include:

For example: money, funds, wealth, prosperity, abundance, wallet, etc.

Another definition of the lexeme "wealth" by T.F. Efremova in the explanatory dictionary of the Russian language describes it as "a large amount of money, valuables, or property." All definitions of "wealth" in the Russian language primarily emphasize the presence, accumulation, and preservation of material and financial assets.

Thus, it can be concluded that proverbs hold significant importance in the linguistic consciousness of individuals from any culture. The enduring relevance of folk proverbs, which have been passed down through generations, signifies their embodiment of essential knowledge and national characteristics unique to a particular culture. It is crucial to recognize that these proverbs reflect the timeless values and collective wisdom of a nation.

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Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

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Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
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